

Foreign Experience In Increasing The Competitiveness Of Higher Educational Graduates

Annakulov Kamol Khasanovich

Director of Tashkent Economic and Industrial Technical college

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Annotation. This article analyzes the competitiveness of higher education graduates in the labor market. It emphasizes the need for social partnership between the state, the labor market, and educational institutions to enhance graduates' competitiveness. Foreign experiences, including Japan's corporate training system and the state policies of the USA, Germany, and France, are examined. Recommendations are provided on the employment of university graduates and their professional adaptation in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: labor market, competitiveness, university graduates, social partnership, state policy, foreign experience, employment.

INTRODUCTION.

The competitiveness of higher education graduates in the modern labor market remains one of the pressing problems. While employers are increasingly demanding highly qualified and professionally trained specialists, in many countries the flexibility of higher education graduates in the labor market is decreasing. This is due to the fact that higher education institutions and It requires the establishment of close ties between employers and the improvement of mechanisms for coordinating education and employment by the state.

This article analyzes foreign experiences in increasing the competitiveness of university graduates, including approaches in this area from Japan, the USA, Germany and France. It also provides recommendations on measures that should be taken to increase the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market in Uzbekistan.

The main part.

Nowadays, the competitiveness of future specialists in the labor market is becoming the main indicator of the efficiency of any enterprise. Even

the most prestigious higher education institutions are evaluated by the competitiveness of their graduates. However, recently, in many countries, the decline in the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market has become increasingly alarming.

Increasing the competitiveness of graduates, on the one hand, requires improving the activities of higher education institutions, and on the other hand, it advocates for the interaction of the labor market and higher education entities within the framework of social partnership, which is formed through the development and implementation of measures aimed at coordination by the state.

The subjects that ensure the competitiveness of university graduates are: the state, the labor market, and higher education entities. The state acts as the main center that coordinates the harmonious relations between the labor market and higher education entities, and its tasks are as follows:

First, the most important task of the state is to develop draft laws and ensure the implementation of laws related to the education system; the state

carries out reforms in the higher education system based on a carefully developed concept.

Secondly, only the state can conduct macroeconomic policy in the field of youth employment, put an end to mass youth unemployment and dismissal, ensure social protection for youth, protect the interests of graduates as a social group of employees who do not have sufficient practical and production, as well as social experience, and develop a unified concept of actions aimed at coordinating labor relations between graduates and employers.

For example, in a market environment, the ultimate interests of universities and employers in terms of employment and job placement differ. While the ultimate goal for universities is to prepare competitive graduates, for employers it is to make a huge profit by hiring highly qualified specialists.

Thirdly, the state maintains its high status by financing higher education institutions, and in addition, it is the largest employer. The state plays an important role in managing the higher education system and improving the activities of higher education institutions, ensuring the formation and development of the competitiveness of graduates.

Fourth, in a market economy, the state coordinates the interaction between the labor market and education, provides subsidies, supports the creation and preservation of new jobs for young people, and wants small and medium-sized businesses to get on their feet and develop.

The state coordination mechanism is a set of targeted methods and measures that ensure interaction and communication between entities and regulate the rights, opportunities, guarantees, and responsibilities of interested parties¹.

The state uses economic, organizational, administrative and legal methods in coordination,

which are the state's means of action, serving to achieve goals and solving specific issues.

Economic methods: preferential lending and taxation, budget policies that encourage entrepreneurs to create and maintain new jobs for young people, vocational training, etc.

Organizational methods: youth employment and job placement assistance services, information systems, training and retraining of personnel, organization of a state system of vocational guidance.

Administrative-legislative (legal) methods: determining the procedure for concluding "graduate-employer" employment contracts, introducing mandatory contributions by entrepreneurs to public funds supporting youth employment, allocating quotas for the employment of young people, including graduates, setting the minimum hourly wage, etc. Legal coordination affects the socio-economic development of the region, state structures (organizations, enterprises), their use of employment fund resources.

State coordination is provided by a set of measures that directly and indirectly affect socio-economic processes. Measures of direct influence include: legislation, state investments, loans, subsidies, quotas, social payments, etc.

Indirect impact measures include: budgetary, tax and monetary policy related to the interests and resources of economic entities, legal entities and individuals.

Labor market entities: state authorities and management bodies, employment services, public organizations, employers, recruitment agencies, etc.

Higher education entities: Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, interregional and regional coordination and analytical centers on

¹ Babashkina A.M. Government regulation of national economy. - M.: Finance and statistics, 2006. - P.226.; Elovikov L.A. Ekonomika truda: Uchebnoe posobie. - Omsk:

the problems of graduate employment and adaptation to market conditions, universities, employment support centers of universities.

Studying the experience of developed countries in determining the competitiveness of specialists allows us to identify a specific approach to preparing and adapting university graduates to the labor market. Therefore, in our study, we also consider the experience of foreign countries in increasing the competitiveness of university graduates.

For example, in Japan, competition begins at the university entrance exam stage: all school graduates want to enter a prestigious university, knowing full well that they will be able to get a job in a well-known company after graduation, since the only aspect that companies pay attention to is the name and prestige of the institution that awarded the diploma.

Many Japanese companies are not interested in hiring people who specialize in a particular field. The value is represented by a specialist who is able to work effectively in a team, who fully identifies his interests with the interests of the company. The specialist is actually “educated” by the company and undergoes an internship at its expense.

In Japan, with its lifetime employment system and salary structure that emphasizes promotion and seniority, most employees are expected to stay with the same company until retirement. As a result, companies invest heavily in their on-the-job training programs. In this context, for many large companies, starting a job marks the beginning of a career for employees. Therefore, the main criteria for employment are not qualifications, but the ability and willingness to learn that they demonstrate.

In the Japanese practice of training specialists, special attention is paid to the development of such a quality as integrity of thinking. Enterprises are entrusted with social

responsibility for the development of the employee, his self-improvement. Analysis of such an approach shows that the system of training specialists should be based on such a command of society and ensure the development of such qualities in the process of training. Ultimately, this will help increase competitiveness.

In this regard, in 2012, at the initiative of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, a 3-year national project “Improving Higher Education for Production Needs” was launched in Japan, in which 147 universities participated. The main goal of the project was to create a competitive educational environment for Japanese universities in order to cultivate the innovative qualities of human resources. It was also aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the higher education system in developing the competitiveness of graduates by disseminating information on labor market problems and strategies between universities and companies. In addition, one of the main goals of the project was to identify the needs of industrial enterprises and companies for specific qualifications of graduates.

Even in the age of new technologies, it is not the possession of traditional knowledge and skills that is important, but continuous learning. Firms themselves teach newcomers the necessary knowledge and skills. For a company, it is important not only for a graduate to have specific knowledge, especially in the humanities, but also for him to be able to maintain the traditions of teamwork, harmony and solidarity. The main requirement for business for the higher education system is to train creative, unconventional thinking, capable of innovation and initiative.

Thus, in the Japanese experience, to increase competitiveness in the labor market, students (future graduates) are required to develop both professional and “hard” and “soft” skills during their studies at the university, that is, the ability to

correctly identify and set priorities for the future, professional growth, self- and time management, effective work and teamwork, stress resistance, etc.

Without underestimating the importance of measures aimed at increasing the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market, it should be noted that the interaction of higher education institutions and industry is of crucial importance for the socio-psychological, professional adaptation and employment of graduates, but this process has not yet been sufficiently developed. The lack of targeted programs and projects in this area leaves university graduates under the threat of unemployment.

In particular, the experience of advanced European countries such as Germany, France, Austria, Denmark, Switzerland, and the Netherlands, as well as developed countries in North America, has proven that state-sponsored cooperation between vocational schools and manufacturing enterprises is highly effective ².

The example of these countries shows that the active state policy in the employment of young people, including graduates of educational institutions, provides great assistance in the issue of employment. The employment of graduates of educational institutions is carried out through the regulatory and legal regulation of labor relations between employers and graduates, a financial mechanism, specialized social and state services that ensure consistent communication with employers, etc. An infrastructure is in place to support youth employment and their employment: regional employment services provide free advice to young people on choosing a profession, distribute information about apprenticeships (internships, internships) at enterprises, and a

standard employment contract has been established by the employers' union and trade unions within the framework of the tariff agreement, which is concluded between the "training enterprise" and the future specialist.

For example, in France, youth employment policies are supported through programs that allow future professionals to both study and work in a company. Participating companies are provided with tax incentives, including tax deductions for those who implement apprenticeship programs.

Enterprises that have established any form of vocational guidance for unemployed youth, whether it is apprenticeship or other alternative forms of vocational guidance, are exempt from paying contributions to social funds. If an enterprise employs young people who have undergone vocational training within the framework of state programs, its contributions to social security funds are reduced by 50 percent, and by 25 percent if it employs unemployed young people who have not received education ³.

The US Workforce Equity Training Act provides for subsidies from the federal budget to states for training and employment of the unemployed, and 40 percent of these funds are allocated to programs for young people. The total number of teachers, instructors, and direct supervisors who teach their subordinates work methods and skills and who are officially engaged in industrial training exceeds 45 thousand people. 7.5 thousand large companies spend \$ 2 billion annually on training their employees. A similar situation can be observed in Western Europe and Japan. In Germany, 9 billion marks are spent annually on training organized by companies on their territory. In China, in order to train personnel

² Vinslav Yu. Professional education and economics: micro-level integrative processes // Russian economic magazine. - 2005. - No. 7-8. - S.2 5.

³ Rudenko G.G. Internal and external market: the mechanism

of balance development. Ministry of Education RF. Rossiyskaya ekonomicheskaya academy named after G.V. Plekhanova. - Moscow, 2003. - P.127.

to world standards, absorb foreign experience, introduce advanced technologies, and also due to the increasing number of joint ventures, the tradition of inviting trainers from other countries is widespread⁴.

Studying the experience of the United States allows us to talk about the diversity of forms of active participation of business in the training of the workforce in this country. Career centers operating in US universities (private and public) are widespread, which serve to strengthen the connection between the educational institution and the employer.

An American student strives to find a job as early as their first year, and this is the key to obtaining a profession, not a diploma. Thus, competition among graduates begins during their student years. Although the status of a university graduate is an important factor, it is not considered a determinant of the competitiveness of a graduate.

Finland's experience in increasing the competitiveness of its higher education graduates is noteworthy. Students in the country have the fewest class hours among developed countries (classes start between 8-9 am and end by 2 pm), but they still achieve very good results.

In Finland, students learn more languages. They learn Finnish from the first day of school. At the age of 9, they start learning Swedish. At the age of 11, they are encouraged to learn a third language (usually English). Many students are learning a fourth language by the age of 13⁵.

To help their students with their professional development and employment, Chinese higher education institutions organize job fairs, meetings with employers and companies, conduct courses

and programs on career planning, creating their own businesses, and finance students in creating their own businesses through a grant system.

According to statistics, 60% of the country's graduating students find a job in their specialty within the first year after graduating from university, including 3% of students who successfully create their own businesses, 40% work in another specialty or are looking for a job⁶.

The practice of advanced countries living on the basis of a market economy has proven that active measures of state policy in the field of youth employment serve to increase the effectiveness of vocational education. The costs incurred to promote youth employment (this area is usually allocated first) are long-term and are assessed from the point of view of the national interests of the state, ensuring the development of the national economy in the long term. Because the failure to invest in the cultural, educational and spiritual potential of young people can lead to extremely negative consequences for both the individual and the nation.

It is worth noting that constructive, positive results in increasing the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market can be achieved through cooperation between all stakeholders - the state, higher education, and employers - based on the principles of social partnership aimed at regulating their mutual interests.

Social partnership in the labor market is regulated by international legal norms (International Labor Organization (ILO) conventions and recommendations, Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Presidential decrees and resolutions, etc.) and other regulatory documents.

⁴ Costin L.A. Rossiysky rynek is in the street. Voprosy theory, history, practice. Akademia truda i sotsialnykh otnosheniy. - Moscow, 1998. - P.229.

⁵ [Finland education system to oneself originality What is it ?](#)

⁶ Ustimko, Ya. O. Osobennosti karernogo stanovleniya i trudoustroystva studentov (na primere Rossii, Kitaya i Yuzhnoi Korei) / Ya. O. Ustimko, E. K. Mishurova. — Text: neposredstvennyy // Molodoy uchenyy. — 2017. — No. 2 (136). — S. 522-525.

The main principles of social partnership are:

- obedience to the law;
- equality;
- openness and transparency;
- universality;
- independence;
- impartiality;
- mutual respect, consideration of interests, and responsibility;
- Voluntary acceptance of obligations ⁷.

of research, the tasks of social partnership are, first of all, to form optimal ways of operating higher education institutions, taking into account the needs of the production sector for labor, as well as the characteristics of the economy, the development of the industrial sector, the innovativeness of small businesses, and the presence of large enterprises, and thereby create conditions for the activities of higher education institutions to prepare personnel potential in advance that meets the reasonable requirements of the current and future labor market.

Secondly, to address specific issues inherent in labor relations between employers and university graduates.

Third, provide social assistance to university graduates who do not have sufficient social and work experience and are entering into employment relations with an employer for the first time.

The main object of social partnership between state structures, employers and higher education (HEIs) are HE graduates. HE graduates enter the labor market with their “special products” – their profession and level of qualification to show to the employer. That is, HE graduates enter the labor market, firstly, as a product of HEI activities, secondly, as a subject of labor relations, and thirdly, as a unique independent subject with qualifications, profession, needs, interests, attitudes, goals. HE

graduates enter the labor market with the aim of finding a job.

On the other hand, employers in the labor market place demands on university graduates: the ability to quickly adapt to the constant change in production technologies, the ability to demonstrate a high level of professional mobility. The most important goals of employers as entrepreneurs: the desire to make a profit, the need to implement an idea, goal, innovation. Entrepreneurs create public organizations in order to protect and achieve their interests. The goal of university graduates is to realize their competitiveness, and the goal of employers is to maximize profits. Therefore, it is necessary to coordinate the mutual needs of university graduates and employers.

Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that increasing the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market is a holistic problem, and its solution requires a targeted approach. The organizational aspect is a priority, which includes the following areas: conducting a targeted policy in the field of youth employment, improving the areas of activity of universities, social partnership of entities ensuring the competitiveness of university graduates, organizational and methodological support of the activities of university employment centers.

Targeted state policy on youth employment is carried out using the method of targeted programs, that is, it relies on targeted legislative acts, the development of a procedure for regulatory and legal coordination of "graduate-employer" labor relations, targeted projects, and programs.

Improving the areas of activity of higher education institutions is carried out through the “Higher Education Institutions-Labor Market-Production” scheme, which takes into account the current and prospective needs of the production

⁷ Uzbekistan " Social " of the Republic partnership about "

Article 4 of the Law // <https://lex.uz/docs/2468214>.

network and the labor market. Competitive personnel for enterprises can be implemented based on the algorithm we propose: improvement of vocational training technology by higher education institutions, marketing activities of higher education institutions, measures for the socio-psychological and professional adaptation of graduates to the labor market. The general principle of the activities of higher education institutions in choosing a model for training competitive graduates should be determined by the current and future needs of the innovative economy and the small business, service, industrial, production-innovation sectors of the region for personnel. Also, each higher education institution should have an employment assistance center.

It is proposed to assess the competitiveness of graduates, which is formed and developed in the process of the activities of higher education institutions, according to three indicators: professional qualifications, motivational potential, marketing potential. We imagine such a form of activity of higher education institutions that would not only serve the formation and development of a mechanism of harmonious relations between higher education and the labor market, but would also be recognized as a necessary condition for creating a quality workforce.

Social partnership between the state, employers and higher education_It determines and coordinates the rights, limitations and opportunities of subjects, the interests of the parties, based on economic, organizational, administrative-legislative, socio-psychological, direct and indirect principles, forms and methods, and forms the procedure, norms and foundations of their mutual relations. This requires the creation of an organizational structure (Committee, Council) consisting of representatives of the subjects entering into mutual relations at the regional level - state authorities and local self-government bodies,

higher education, employers' associations, trade unions, the Federal State Employment Service and other interested organizations.

In Uzbekistan, graduates of higher education institutions acquire a lot of knowledge and skills during their studies, but the problem lies in the lack of the necessary connection between the education market and the labor market. It is known that the employment of a large number of students is a positive factor for the university, but its importance for the regional economy is also significant. Recently, the acute problems associated with youth employment have become an important factor in increasing the responsibility for the subsequent employment of graduates of educational institutions. Therefore, there is a need to most accurately characterize the requirements for a graduate in terms of real production conditions and the specifics of the local labor market (profession, qualifications, skills), and secondly, it is explained by the need to develop a system for adapting students to working conditions. According to some scholars, "any mismatch between the programs being taught and the skills needed in the workplace is a problematic issue for the country's future." One of the traditional ways to address the problem of the relationship between educational services and the labor market is to conclude long-term contracts between the educational institution and the employer and involve him in the educational process.

Conclusion.

Social partnership between the state, higher education institutions and employers is important for increasing the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market. Analyzed foreign experiences show that the close connection between the education system and the labor market ensures the professional adaptation of specialists and increases the employment rate.

In Japan, companies' training of employees at

their own expense, in the USA and Germany, state subsidies for the vocational training system, and in France, the use of programs to provide employment for young specialists through tax incentives have yielded effective results. In Uzbekistan, it is necessary to strengthen close cooperation between educational institutions and employers, guide graduates towards professional adaptation, and improve educational programs taking into account the real needs of the labor market.

Thus, a systematic approach and comprehensive measures are required to increase the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market. State-coordinated mechanisms, cooperation between higher education institutions and employers, and improvement of vocational training programs will help solve these problems .

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